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Diversification vs. specialization from the perspective of research programmes: a complexity approach

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Introduction

Through policy instruments, policies are designed and government goals are pursued. Understanding how countries, through their agencies, implement research funding instruments in relation to the amount of investment and policy priorities is therefore critical in Research and Innovation (R&I). In the last few years, research funding instruments have become strategic issues in science, technology and innovation policy studies (Lepori and Reale, 2019). For this reason, we think that a different perspective is needed to reduce the dimensionality of information on programs and use metrics that would allow to deepen the configuration of funding portfolios and policy mixes of programs by focusing on instruments characteristics, actors involved, and topics addressed in different European countries. This work tackles a new perspective that has been less explored in the literature: the complexity of government research funding instruments.

The paper deepens the diversification/specialisation of nine European countries (Austria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Germany, Italy, Norway, Switzerland, and United Kingdom) in Key Enabling Technologies (KETs) and Societal Grand Challenges (SGCs), analysing a part of research public arena, namely the project funding instruments designed and managed by national Research Funding Organizations (RFOs) for the year 2018. It aims at connecting research policy instruments and KETs and SGCs orientation to highlight the plurality of national R&I policy strategies.

We begin by identifying the funding instrument objectives in terms of KETs and SGCs through the official documents of such RFOs (for more details, see Reale et al., 2022), and developing complexity measures to examine the diversification/specialization by RFO.

Assuming the universal and interconnected nature of both KETs and SGCs, as well as the reality that a country's actions on one objective will always have an influence on the achievement of the other KETs and SGCs, our purpose is twofold: i) we want to improve the qualitative and quantitative understanding on KET/SGC interactions; ii) identify central and peripheral topics (KET and SGC sub-categories) by RFO in the analysed networks.

From a funding instrument standpoint, the main question is: how are RFOs performing in their challenge toward KETs and SGCs? We address this question by treating RFOs and global challenges (both for KETs and SGCs) as a complex bipartite network.

This paper follows the approach used for qualifying the knowledge composition of economic systems developed by Hidalgo and Hausmann (2009) to investigate the policy orientation of RFOs of nine European countries in terms of diversity, ubiquity, and complexity. The plurality of valuable information contained in an economy, according to Hausmann et al. (2014), is connected to its complexity. According to the two authors, the composition of a country's productive output reflects economic complexity (EC). On the subject of our proposal, the project funding instrument orientation of RFOs can be used as a proxy for the complexity of public R&D funding.

We think that an approach based on the research funding instrument can reveal the nature of research policy dynamics and assist policymakers with aspects of the instrument design process, such as data measurement and benchmarking, target prioritizing, and progress tracking with respect to many global challenges.

Conceptual Framework

The ability of public R&D investments to have positive effects on science and society by tackling social problems, developing challenges and giving answers for enhancing the quality of citizens' lives is one of the most important and recurring policy issues. Many governments have embarked on funding reforms, expanding their strategic-planning ability, and paying more attention to the social and economic environment. RFOs use public R&D funding to influence and steer the research activities of actors in a particular field by selecting specific projects to achieve policy goals (Reale and Zinilli, 2017). Recent papers emphasized the role of funders in shaping scientific research toward a societal impact by "targeting" thematic orientation and anticipating a process of "enforcement" intended to ensure that researchers meet the targets (Schneider et al., 2019). Other research has looked at the tensions that exist between RFOs that manage project funding and the government; RFOs struggle to maintain their flexibility and ability to pursue their own goals without being steered by the government (Lepori and Reale, 2019). It was also emphasized that in the national context, RFO differentiation might lead to either a broadening of objectives and strategies or a restricting of goals and priorities (Whitley et al., 2018).

We believe there is a gap in the literature on funding instrument diversification of RFOs and orientation toward technological and societal challenges. In particular, the way in which KETs and SGCs could relate to research policy instruments has been left unexplored. The purpose of this paper is to fill that gap by looking into the role that KETs and SGCs have in the funding instruments portfolio of different RFOs. The R&I policies for KETs and SGCs are essentially focused with Europe's position and competitiveness in these spheres. In terms of KETs in Europe, the specialization with respect to some topics appears to be an indicator of a country's difficulty in dealing with the challenges that society has today (Reiss et al., 2016). For instance, research diversification on KETs can play an important role in a variety of future goods and activities (innovation space of a country). Research investment is also crucial for dealing with the SGCs. Specialization and diversification are two aspects of the same phenomenon that together the actors involved push to investigate the variety of elements to combine with a complexity approach. This leads directly to the central concept of the literature on economic complexity: developed countries are not only more diversified, but also more complex

(Hausmann and Hidalgo, 2011). The Economic Complexity approach uses international trade data as a bipartite network, with countries linked to the products that they export. The empirical finding that the most competitive countries tend to diversify their export basket, whereas emerging countries are only able to export few products, often those exported by many other countries. As a result, competitive countries have a highly diversified export basket, whereas developing countries tend to export ubiquitous products, according to the economic complexity perspective.

Taking this into account, a RFO that only has a few funding instruments directed at a few KET and SGC categories is not very diversified. In contrast, if the funding instruments are aimed at a variety of categories, the agencies are less specialized and therefore diversified. The instrument orientation in terms of KETs and SGCs, as well as the resources invested in the specific instrument, determine the agency's complexity.

The paper addresses two research questions:

Q1) analysing the project funding instruments, what are the most diversified and specialized RFOs in terms of KETs and SGCs?

Q2) which are the most ubiquity KET and SGC items?

The framework of research policy complexity used in this paper is entangled with different dimensions: i) country dimension, each country is characterized by different paradigmatic models of research policy and governance context; ii) agency dimension (or RFO dimension), deepening elements related to their organizational forms and critical mass; iii) research funding instrument dimension, their orientation and mission, as well as the funding volumes.

A way of illustrating how the complexity of research policy instruments arises from a central understanding of these three dimensions is to posit that the complexity takes two forms:

- the number and typology of RFOs by country;
- orientation of research funding instruments towards technological and societal challenges, as well as the funding volume.

Through complexity indices we reduce the dimensionality of these several entities involved and at the same time preserve more information than mere aggregates.

Data and methods

The empirical basis for the analyzes is data from the EFIL database.¹ In this paper, we examine data from the European countries for the year 2018. For 2018, there is a total of 41 RFOs and 232 project funding instruments. We take 70 categories into account for SGCs and 66 categories for KETs (for further details, see Reale et al., 2022)

We identify a series of indexes that can be used to disentangle the diversification and specialization of RFOs from nine European countries.

We calculated the Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) to compare the instrument orientation by agency. In our case, this index indicates the ratio between the funding share of KET\SGC category (c) in an agency (a) and the amount of funding allocated to KET\SGC category in the general dataset.

¹ EFIL - European dataset of public R&D funding instruments is one of the facility included in the distributed research infrastructure RISIS

We grouped the information on what RFOs (a) fund several programs related to KET\SGC category (c) into a matrix (M) with dimensions $a \times c$ (bipartite network), as in the economic complexity literature. If an RFO funds instruments oriented to a specific KET\SGC above a given threshold (0.1), the elements in the matrix assume a value of 1 (and zero otherwise).

Such structure reflects the fact that some agencies fund a large set of KET\SGC categories (highly diversified agencies), and some categories appear to be funded (via policy instruments) by most agencies (ubiquitous categories).

RFOs can be based on the diversity and ubiquity of project funding instrument orientation related to KET and SGC categories. Diversity is given by the number of KET\SCG categories covered by the funding instruments for each agency. Ubiquity is given by the spread of the categories among agencies in the nine analysed countries. Complexity can be captured by the interaction between ubiquity and diversity.

Adopting the different complexity approaches in economic context (Hidalgo and Hausmann, 2009) to policy instruments for public R&D funding, we can explain intra and inter-agency category distribution (both for KETs and SGCs), and variability by two indices of complexity, respectively for RFO and category. An agency with high Complexity index is characterized by high diversity, i.e., it is oriented to many categories, while low index is characterized by low diversity and low complexity. A category with high Complexity index is characterized by low ubiquity and is present in agencies with high complexity, while low Complexity index is characterized by high ubiquity and is present in agencies with low complexity.

Results

In the following figure, we show the normalized RCAs for KETs (figure 1) and SGCs (figure 2). The purpose of this metric is to figure out which category an agency is more specialized in than others and so appears to have a competitive advantage in. RCA value is normalized between +1 (comparative advantages in the appropriate categories) and -1 (comparative disadvantages). The greater the RCA values in figures 1a and 1b, the lighter the colour.

Fig. 1 Matrix Agency x KET category

In the above figure, we compare the relative specialization and comparative advantages of each agency by KET category. In several KET categories, Norway, Denmark, and the United Kingdom agencies have a significant comparative advantage over the other agencies. The United Kingdom unlike Norway and Denmark also has a larger number of agencies.

In the figure 2, we compare the relative specialization and comparative advantages of each agency by SGC category.

Fig. 2 Matrix Agency x SGC category

Looking at the SGCs, Norway’s agency, along with Czech Republic’s and the United Kingdom’s, appears to be more focused on societal issues.

Table 1 lists the top ten and bottom ten agencies in terms of category heterogeneity. We focused on the variety measure for both the KET and SGC instrument orientations.

Tab. 1 Variety measure by agency

	Variety Agency ranking on KET	Variety Agency ranking on SGC
TOP	NO5001	NO5001
	DK5002	DE5001
	CZ5004	DK5001
	UK5002	UK5003
	CZ5009	UK5009
	DK5001	UK5011
	UK5004	UK5021
	UK5018	CZ5008
	CH5001	DK5002
	DE5004	UK5002
BOTTOM	CZ5006	CZ5002
	CZ5007	AT5003
	CZ5008	CZ5001
	DE5003	CZ5003
	DE5006	CZ5007
	EE5002	DE5002
	UK5016	DE5003
	UK5020	DE5006
	DK5003	EE5002
	EE5003	EE5003

In terms of KET and SGC variety, RCN (Norway) is at the top of the list, while ETF (Estonia) is at the bottom.

A possible technique is to define a projection graph derived from the original set of bipartite interactions to grasp the relations between agencies induced by their KET/SGC categories. The goal is to bind the various agencies together through a link whose strength is determined by the quantity of categories (both for KET and SGC) they are oriented. The figure 3 is based on the proximity matrix we created, which took into account the similarity between agencies. Here, we glance at the network of agencies obtained from an agency-agency adjacency matrix for KETs and SGCs.

Fig. 3 Proximity Based Network Projection for RFOs

The network visualization reveals the differences in the structure of the proximity network between agencies in KET and SGC context. We can see that some agencies are closer and tend to be in the core of the graph, while others are more isolated and on the periphery of the graph. It is worth noting that some agencies in Austria, the Czech Republic, and Germany are well connected in the SGC network, forming a dense cluster. The size of the node is proportional to the agency's funding share. In 2018, it is possible to see that the agency RCN (Norway) funds a larger quota in project funding instruments, followed by DFG (Germany).

The proximity matrix used to create the inter-agency projections shows that the RFOS from Norway, Denmark, Germany, and the United Kingdom have complementary instrument orientations. There is not overlap between agencies in the same country, indicating that these countries have a high level of diversification and a clear role in terms of agency orientation. Similarly, we can project the bipartite network into a category-category network. It is possible to connect two categories if they are funded by the same one or more agencies and giving this link a weight proportionate to the number of agencies which project research instruments are oriented towards both categories.

Figure 4 shows the proximity between KET categories.

Fig. 4 Proximity Based Network Projection for KET

KET

When we look at the category's hierarchical structure, we can see that a few categories representing the policy orientation of the instruments are more common between agencies and between instruments within the same agency. We can see the connections between several KET categories in the “nanobiotechnology” family (in the upper right), for example. This means that some instruments are oriented towards microscale devices, indicating a strong focus on this specific topic. Categories such as “biologics”, “biomimetics” and “biomaterials” are also connected and belong to the same topic cluster.

Figure 5 shows the proximity between SGC categories.

Fig.5 Proximity Based Network Projection for SGC

SGC

It becomes clear that some instruments have a more generic policy orientation, while others have a strong orientation. The cluster “security” is a good example for the latter case. Of course, this reflects the type of RFO (eg. Research Councils tend to be generic in the policy orientation). In this case, the network configuration is composed of multiple layers. In comparison to the KET network, categories are linked to far fewer other categories. This indicates that the instruments are well-defined in terms of social challenges; the instruments are much more oriented.

Ubiquity measure accounts for the level of diffusion, and hence the commonality of the sectors. In our case, ubiquity can be thought of as the variety of instruments that each category has. The ubiquity by category is shown in Table 2.

Tab. 2 Ubiquity ranking of KET and SGC categories

	Ubiquity KET category ranking	Ubiquity SGC category ranking
TOP	genomics_3	education_6
	biomimetics_3	employment_6
	biologics_3	global_engagement_6
	environmental_biotechnology_3	knowledge_transfer_6
	regenerative_medicine_3	carbon_footprint_2
	gene_delivery_3	cultural_heritage_6
	cell_delivery_3	democracy_6
	expression_systems_3	waste_management_and_recycli
	industrial_microbiology_3	catastrophe_fighting_5
	nanoscale_materials_5	digital_security_5
	BOTTOM	nanoscale_de
nanoscience_technique		digital_security
nanoscience_techniques_and_ins		hydro_power_3
nanotechnologies_for_manufactu		intelligent_transport_7
nucleic_acid_th		noise_2
regener		photovoltaics_3
regenerative_medi		rail_transport_7
rf_technologies_4		security_monitoring
software_for_manufacturing_1		water_systems_2
stem_cell_biotechnology_3		renewable_heating_and_coolin

Our results show that for KET “genomics” and “biomimetics” are more common (ubiquitous) than “stem cell biotechnology” or “software for manufacturing”. The top categories are all related to the KET macro category “Industrial biotechnology”. For SGC the most common categories belonging to the SGC macro category “society”. “Security” and “climate change and the environment” are two of the other major macro categories.

Conclusions

Studying the complexity of research policy instruments research is important because it allows us to gain a better understanding of how politics are evolving. This approach to the complexity of research funding instruments will provide new information for scholars and policymakers. First, this analysis could enhance our understanding of the technological and societal target orientation that drive project funding instruments. Second, it could help European countries and RFOs to find a more precise space for KETs and SGCs in their research policy agenda. In terms of project funding instrument orientation, the results show a clear differentiation between agencies and, as a result, between countries. In terms of KET and SGC instrument orientation, Norway, the United Kingdom, Czech Republic, and Denmark are more diversified. Furthermore, for Norway, Denmark, Germany, and the United Kingdom the degree of overlap among the categories is low. This means that there is a clear difference in instrument orientation, as well as between agencies within the same country with distinct and well-defined policy goals. Furthermore, to answer our second question, the funding instruments are mainly

oriented towards “industrial biotechnology” for KET and “society” for SGC. There appears to be little opportunity for sustainability and climate change-related categories.

Paper limitation and further research

In this paper we look at 2018 project funding instrument data. However, the volatility of a complexity rating, or how it varies over time, is an interesting feature. We expect ranking variations, both for KET\SGC, to be slow or with few variation over the years. This is due to the fact that changing policy in terms of funding quotas and policy orientation is a time-consuming process. The next step will be to look into the complexity of projects funding instrument over the time.

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